

An Intent-Based Control and Management Framework for Optical Transport Networks supporting B5G Services Empowered by Large Language Models

ANNA TZANAKAKI,* MARKOS ANASTASOPOULOS, VICTORIA-MARIA ALEVIZAKI

National and Kapodistrian University of Athens, Department of Physics, Athens 15772, Greece

[*atzanakaki@phys.uoa.gr](mailto:atzanakaki@phys.uoa.gr)

Received XX Month XXXX; revised XX Month, XXXX; accepted XX Month XXXX; posted XX Month XXXX (Doc. ID XXXXX); published XX Month XXXX

This study focuses on the development of an Intent-based Networking (IBN) control and management framework automating operations of beyond 5G (B5G) infrastructures supported by optical transport networks to interconnect radio access and core networks. Currently, these infrastructures operate in accordance with the Software Defined Networking (SDN) and Network Function Virtualization (NFV) paradigm, relying on complex Northbound and Southbound Interfaces to expose their (network) capabilities and apply suitable configuration policies to B5G infrastructure. B5G Infrastructures are expected to operate over complex heterogenous transport network and compute domains, each having its own programming language and interfaces. To address the increased complexity of this approach, the present study relies on Generative Artificial Intelligence (GenAI) and Large Language models (LLMs) to significantly simplify the interaction between different layers and domains, through automated translation of configuration policies from one domain to another. More specifically, the developed GenAI models are used to support automated operations of B5G infrastructures by: a) translating high level intents provided by network operators expressed in the form of a natural language into auto-generated optimization code used by the orchestrator and, b) creating auto-configuration policies for the optical transport network. The semantic accuracy and complexity of the proposed framework to generate appropriate configuration policies is experimentally tested over an optical transport network interconnecting the radio access and core networks of a B5G infrastructure.

1. Introduction

Beyond 5G (B5G) networks are expected to offer ubiquitous and advanced services to support the next generation sustainable, fair and resilient Information and Communication Technology (ICT) ecosystems. This introduces the need for extended connectivity of a huge number of devices, extreme and varying levels of capacity and bandwidth granularity, increased degree of

user mobility in support of a great variety of services with strict sustainability, efficiency and autonomy goals. In view of these, the most realistic architectural approach towards the realization of the 6G vision involves integration of a variety of heterogeneous advanced Radio Access Network (RAN) technologies and the associated compute resources, controlled through the mobile core network. In this context, high-capacity optical transport networks play a key role providing flexible connectivity between the various B5G technologies, systems, domains and the internet.

However, to enable seamless operations across a multiplicity of technologies, domains, infrastructures, services and businesses, there is a need for solutions offering improved automation with real-time decision-making capabilities. These will facilitate handling of complex interactions between different sets of network devices and domains in an efficient and practical manner. Towards this direction, network intelligence that allows subscriber-, service- and application-level awareness to be exploited in automating and optimizing network operation can play a key role [1].

Intent-based networking (IBN) is an emerging networking approach that has been proposed over the past few years to offer increased level of intelligence in communications networks [2]. In contrast to conventional communication systems that rely on manual processes for their configuration, IBN defines a set of fully automated tools for the management and operation of the entire system. Using IBN, network administrators define a set of high-level business objectives and service characteristics known as *intents*. Based on these intents, the system/network software identifies how the requested business/service objectives can be achieved using Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) techniques [3],[4],[5]. IBN systems can automate time-consuming tasks and provide real-time visibility of the network activities to achieve and validate a given intent. IBN also allows intelligence to be embedded across all layers of the heterogeneous infrastructure enabling each domain to operate autonomously. Therefore, each autonomous domain is able to self-optimize its operation under a specific set of objectives and constraints hiding at the same time the details of the specific domain implementation. In addition, these autonomous domains can predict potential deviations with respect to a given intent and prescribe the necessary actions to ensure that this intent is achieved. This increased degree of intelligence

Figure 1: Intent-Based Architecture and operations per layer: *Business Layer*: (1) The vertical industry manager use this interface to input business intent, (2) Collect the intent. *Service Layer*: (3) Translate the high-level intent into network-specific requirements, *Infrastructure Layer*: (4) Send the intent into the network controller.

enhances the speed of network reaction as well as network flexibility and resilience [3].

In this context, a key aspect of IBN involves the definition of suitable Northbound Interfaces (NBIs) and Southbound Interfaces (SBIs). NBIs are responsible to translate application requirements and constraints into commands that are understandable by the underlying hardware, while SBIs apply the corresponding policies to network devices [6]. For cost efficiency and simplicity reasons, IBN is extending current Software Defined Networking (SDN) principles and adopts the main SDN interfaces. However, the main limitation of existing NBIs is that they suffer high degree of complexity [7]. In response to this, intent based NBIs promise to address this challenge allowing users to create and build complex network applications and services [8]. Although intent NBIs are agnostic to the underlying transport network technology they provide the necessary tools to manage and optimize any technology domain. This is achieved unitizing the main feature of intent NBIs i.e. exposing network objects and capabilities to the upper network layers in an abstracted manner [9]. Therefore, the essential difference between intent-driven and traditional interfaces is that intent-driven interfaces declare WHAT is required to be achieved, rather than HOW to achieve this. Although some initial definitions have been described in [10] the relevant developments are still in a very early phase.

To showcase the feasibility of this vision and extending on our previous work reported in [11], this study proposes and implements an IBN framework that provides coordination, and optimization of a B5G infrastructure integrating multiple individual autonomous domains including radio access, optical transport and core networks so that they can collectively support optimized B5G services. Each domain is managed through intent-driven control loops taking actions at the different architectural layers involved (Figure 1):

- at the “A. Infrastructure Layer” (i.e. optical transport network) to adjust traffic forwarding policies taking optimal routing and traffic steering decisions,
- at the “B. Services Layer” to dynamically update end-to-end policies, considering measurements that can assist in understanding the environment, and the needs of end-users,
- at the “C. Business Layer” ensuring delivery of services according to the agreed functional specification and non-functional requirements expressed by target Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) (e.g. bandwidth, latency, etc.) and Key Value Indicators (KVI) (e.g., service level availability, service level guarantee based on response times, repair times etc.).

To implement this concept, NBIs and SBIs that are used to manage the optical transport network have been enhanced with intent capabilities. The intent based NBIs and SBIs expose the abstracted resource information of the transport network to the upper layer controllers (E2E orchestrator). However, due to the large heterogeneity and increased complexity of the B5G protocol stacks, *incompatibility* issues may arise. In this direction, the development of automatic translation mechanisms for SBIs/NBIs in IBN enables the creation of autonomous transport networks composed of several autonomous domains. These cooperate to support the demanding requirements of B5G use cases enabling the development of vendor-neutral network control solution [12].

The present study extends the state of the art in intent based NBIs through the development of suitable interfaces that allow translation of high level intents to policies defining dynamically the optimal configuration of a multi-domain transport network. To achieve this, we rely on Generative AI (GenAI) and Large Language Models (LLMs) that are used to translate configuration policies

Figure 2: The translator module.

from one domain to another. To implement the corresponding translators, state-of-the-art models based on Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers (BERT) [13]-[14] and Generative Pre-trained Transformer (GPT) are used. These models auto generate the necessary configuration files and Application Programming Interfaces (APIs), exposing available virtual and physical network resources to the upper layers.

In this context, the main contributions of this work are summarized as follows:

a) An intent-based management framework using state-of-the-art GenAI and LLM models to translate high level intents provided by network operators has been developed. These models are expressed in the form of a natural language and support auto-generation of optimization code. The autogenerated optimization code is then used by the infrastructure orchestrator to identify the optimal set of resources (compute and network) that can satisfy the specific intent.

b) The efficiency of state-of-the art LLM models such as GPT to translate business intents into network policies has been extensively evaluated. The relevant evaluations are carried over realistic environments and actual optical network hardware allowing the translation at i) higher network layers to translate intents into optimization code and ii) at lower layers to translate intents into configuration policies for optical network devices.

c) The performance of the proposed framework across different layers of a B5G testbed has been experimentally tested. The corresponding evaluations were carried out usings intents requesting the establishment of service slices with different KVIs and KPIs over a B5G testbed.

The rest of this work is organized as follows: Section 2 provides a brief overview of the IBN principles adopted. Section 3 summarizes basic operating principles and architectures of LLM models and Section 4 includes a description of the scenario and the overall architecture considered in this study along with the main LLM models developed to automate its operations. Section 5 evaluates the performance of LLMs in terms of accuracy and complexity considering the training time to automate the translation of the SBIs and NBIs while Section 6 concludes the paper.

2. Intent Based Networking Principles

We consider an IBN control and management framework to facilitate future automated B5G communication services with enhanced KPIs and KVIs over a multi-domain, multi-technology and

Figure 3: NLP implementation using Transformers [13].

multi-layer network infrastructure. As shown in Figure 1, this infrastructure relies on a multi-technology optical transport network adopting all-optical and optoelectronic switching nodes. This transport network is interconnecting 5G RAN and core segments, providing network services in the form of end-to-end slices. To achieve this, the various building blocks of the disaggregated RAN solution including the Remote Unit (RU), the Distributed Unit (DU), and the Central Unit (CU), the User Plane Function (UPF) and the rest of the core network functions can be flexibly combined to support different infrastructure and service deployment options.

To coordinate the operation of the various components of the system, the IBN concept relies on local controllers¹ which are organized into a hierarchy as shown in Figure 1. This hierarchical approach is used to hide complexity and increase the scalability of the system as local controllers are responsible to manage only a portion of the network without having the full detailed view of the entire system, including various, technology domains and resources [15]. Intents received by higher layer controllers are decomposed into domain-specific subproblems which are assigned to local controllers. This way, the upper layer controllers use the interfaces and APIs of the lower layer controllers to apply the specific configuration rules and policies.

For example, at the *business layer*, network operators, service providers and/or communication service customers can define intents to deliver a specific objective (i.e., network, service, slice) with a guaranteed performance (in terms of throughput, latency, coverage isolation etc.), treating the network as an abstract series of direct connections between hosts, instead of independent interconnected forwarding devices [16]. These high-level intents written in natural (human) language defining and describing business objectives are implemented and coordinated with the support of the end-to-end orchestrator. The high-level intents can be translated into an optimization program that can be ported in the

¹ In the IBN terminology, these controllers are known as Intent Managers.

Figure 4: a)Token embedding: mapping of words into numbers in an d-dimensional space, b) Positional Encoding vectors for the phrase "Create a slice with ultra low delay"

orchestrator to identify the optimal end-to-end policies. In a similar fashion, lower layer controllers may use APIs from existing domain controllers, such as the Radio Intelligent controller (RIC) in the RAN [17], the SDN controllers in the optical transport and core network controllers [18] and take the necessary actions to execute the part of the intent that was delegated to them by the end-to-end system orchestrator.

A promising technology to implement this functionality is the "Translator" module shown in Figure 2. The basic component of the "Translator" is a Natural Language Processing (NLP) module implemented using the "Transformers" AI model (Figure 3) [13]. This AI model comprises an encoder part namely *Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers* (BERT) and a decoder namely *Generative Pre-trained Transformer* (GPT). The BERT model uses the encoder part of the transformer AI architecture so that it understands high level intents provided by users usually written in natural language. The decoder part based on the GPT model is used to generate the response.

To implement the business layer functionalities of IBN, the GPT model is trained to generate as a response the optimization problem to be solved by the orchestrator at the "Services layer". The optimization problems to be generated are designed to provide consensus and avoiding conflicts among the various technology domains (i.e., fair resource allocation policies). At the "Services Layer", the output of the auto-generated optimization problem is used to create configurations for Open Source Management and Orchestration (MANO) (OSM) to instantiate the service slices. This is performed by allocating the necessary resources of the 5G platform and performing a set of configuration actions to enable the required functionality. These include:

- Manipulation of the configuration files according to the output parameters of the optimization problem to facilitate appropriate operation of the 5G platform and its building blocks including the RAN, the UPF, and the rest of the core network functions.

- Configuration of the interfaces required for the interconnection of the RAN with the UPF and the UPF with the external data network .
- Instantiation of the N3 GTP-U tunnel interconnecting the RAN with the UPF.
- In the final step, instantiation of the control plane and user plane functions in order to make the corresponding service slices operational.

Once the service slice has been configured and instantiated, the final step is applied at the "Infrastructure Layer". The translator takes as input the virtual link connectivity requirements expressed in the form of a "YAML Ain't Markup Language" (YAML) descriptor and generates the appropriate configuration files for the underlying transport network, for example, in OpenFlow Configuration and Management Protocol (OF-CONFIG) and Network Configuration Protocol (NETCONF), SCPI or any other device management protocol. The adoption of LLMs to perform automatic interpretation/translation of configuration policies across layers ensures technology agnostic operation of the overall system aligned with the ETSI GR ZSM 011 standard [19]. Based on this approach, any network device can be plugged and configured by the LLM translator without human intervention.

3. Large Language Models Preliminaries

3.1 Introduction

Translation of high-level business requirements written in natural (human) language or domain-specific language into lower layer domain configuration policies is one of the basic components of the IBN architecture. One of the first implementations of translation mechanisms in IBN has been reported in [20], where an intent framework that translates high level policies into service chains while meeting the specified QoS and security levels is proposed. In [22], the authors presented an IBN framework that allows users to express their desired network functionality in the form of easy to grasp intents, which are subsequently translated into P4 code. Using this approach, network control and management can be shifted from an imperative manner – which

Figure 5: NLP implementation using GPT: The attention mechanism.

requires knowledge of the networking protocols and the network topology – to a declarative manner, allowing users to take advantage of the data-plane programmability benefits in an intuitive manner.

Various aspects of intent translation and deployment have been also investigated in [21] where authors use the Intent-Based Network Modeling (NEMO) language, originally introduced in IETF IB-Nemo BoF [23], to develop a reactive configuration and management mechanisms that update automatically the network environment in order to satisfy the requested intent. In a similar study, the authors use LUMI programming language to develop intents using natural language [24]. Other translation methods are also being adopted, such as sequence-to-sequence learning models [25]. Specifically, in [25] the authors developed a framework to translate high-level policies expressed in a Controlled Natural Language (CNL), into low-level flow rules for SDN. In [6], the authors present an NBI that translates high-level requirements to network management operations. Although these studies made significant progress towards the development of intent-based NBIs, they suffer some shortcomings [26]. Specifically, they require policies described “in a particular syntax, such as CNL and Intents that are hard to interpret. Furthermore, they do not offer an interpretation bridge between management policies and AI notations”. Very recently, the idea to apply LLMs to configure network devices has been proposed [27] with the most prominent approach relying on the “transformer” AI model [13]. In the following subsection, a brief overview of these models and their application in the management of 5G platforms is provided.

3.2 Transformers AI models

The basic architecture of the Transformers AI model is shown in Figure 3. The transformer comprises two main components: a) the encoder stack comprising N_x identical encoding layers and, b) the decoding stack with N_x identical decoding layers.

The input sequence in the encoder part is initially processed by the tokenization and the input embedding block. Through tokenization, inputs in the form of free text provided by the users are converted into a sequence of elements. For example, in case that a business requirement to create an “ultra low delay slice” across the 5G infrastructure arises a high-level intent such as “Create a slice with ultra low delay” is generated. This high-level intent is then transformed into a set of elements (tokens). This is performed

through the application of a tokenizer, such as the BertTokenizer², that transforms the high level intent into a set \mathbf{X} with elements (tokens) where $\mathbf{x}_i \in [\text{'create', 'a', 'slice', 'with', 'ultra', 'low', 'delay'}]$ representing the words of the intent. Specifically, each element \mathbf{x}_i is a vector that encodes the meaning of the word in such a way that the words closer in the vector space have similar meaning. A typical example of this process is shown in Figure 4(a) where the distance and direction between the vectors “optical” and “networks” is similar, reflecting the similarity and relationships among these words. Adding up two or more token vectors a *sentence vector* is constructed. For example, assuming that vectors \mathbf{x}_1 , \mathbf{x}_2 and \mathbf{x}_3 are used for the elements ‘create’, ‘a’ and ‘slice’, respectively, then, the summation $\mathbf{x}_1 + \mathbf{x}_2 + \mathbf{x}_3$ models the sentence “create a slice”.

It is clear that by changing the order of the vectors i.e., $\mathbf{x}_1 + \mathbf{x}_3 + \mathbf{x}_2$, a different phrase is formed which however has the same vector representation. To avoid this event, the positional encoding block has been added in the transformer architecture. The positional encoding block keeps track of the positions of the words in a sentence by adding a positional vector \mathbf{t}_i to each word \mathbf{x}_i . The position of a word \mathbf{x}_i can be modeled as a vector $\mathbf{x}'_i = \mathbf{x}_i + \mathbf{t}_i$. Through this approach, positional encoders ensure that *sentence vectors* $\mathbf{x}'_1 + \mathbf{x}'_2 + \mathbf{x}'_3$ and $\mathbf{x}'_1 + \mathbf{x}'_3 + \mathbf{x}'_2$ are different.

The values of \mathbf{t}_i are calculated using *sinusoidal functions* with different frequencies to encode the position of each element in a sequence. For example, assuming that the original sentence has a length L and the element of interest was originally in the k^{th} position within this sentence, the positional encoding will be calculated through the following equations:

$$P_k(2i) = \sin\left(\frac{k}{n^{2i/d}}\right) \quad (1a)$$

$$P_k(2i + 1) = \cos\left(\frac{k}{n^{2i/d}}\right) \quad (1b)$$

where (1a) models the even (i.e., positions 0, 2, 4,...) and (1b) the odd possible positions (1, 3, 5...) of the token in the output embedding. In these equations:

- d is the dimension (number of elements) of the output embedding (text to be generated)
- i position index taking values in the range $0 \leq i < d/2$.

² https://www.tensorflow.org/text/api_docs/python/text/BertTokenizer

Figure 6: Optimization code generation using Transformers.

- n is a user defined scalar.

Some typical numerical values of the positional encoding vectors for the phrase “Create a slice with ultra low delay” with $d = 7$ and $n = 100$ is shown in Figure 4(b).

The output of the positional encoder is then passed through the multi-head *self-attention* mechanism. The self-attention mechanism uses as input the positional encoded vector x'_i which is transformed into vector z_i . A simplified view of the attention mechanism is shown in Figure 5. This is achieved by calculating the dot product of x'_i with three vectors namely queries, keys and values described with matrices W_Q , W_k and W_v , respectively. The output of the multiplication are the vectors q_i , k_i and v_i :

$$x'_i W_Q = q_i \quad (2)$$

$$x'_i W_k = k_i \quad (3)$$

$$x'_i W_v = v_i \quad (4)$$

In the subsequent step, q_i is multiplied with k_i and normalized by \sqrt{d} . The product $q_i k_i$ takes higher values when a high correlation between input tokens and matrices W_Q , W_k exists. The attention mechanism is followed by a Feedforward block. The feedforward block in the Transformer model takes the output of the attention block and passes it through a series of fully connected layers. These layers apply non-linear transformations to the input, allowing the model to make a prediction regarding the next word in the sequence. The feedforward network is usually implemented using Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) neural networks. In the final step, the output of the feedforward network is used as input in the Softmax Layer to transform results into probabilities (each possible outcome take values in the range of 0 to 1 and the summation of all possible outcomes is 1), where the highest scores correspond to the highest probabilities. Finally, the calculated attention weights are multiplied with the value matrix (v_i), leading to a weighted combination of the value vectors. Training of the model is performed applying the Adam optimizer [28]. In summary, the attention mechanism tries to represent the query as a weighted linear combination of value vectors (V), while

the weights are determined by the correlation between the query and keys (K).

4. Overall Intent-based Architecture using LLMs

The overall platform covering business, service, and infrastructure layer operations is shown in Figure 1. As can be seen each layer operates in a self-operating mode, while the details associated with the domain implementation, operations, and the functions within the domain are not visible to the other domains or layers. At the business layer, network operators, service provides and/or communication service customers can define intents to deliver a specific objective (i.e., network, service, slice) with a guaranteed performance (in terms of throughput, latency, coverage, isolation etc.), treating the network as an abstract series of direct connections between hosts, instead of independent interconnected forwarding devices.

To implement this functionality, the high-level intents written in natural (human) language defining and describing business objectives are translated into an optimization model written in General Algebraic Modeling System (GAMS)/ A Mathematical Programming Language (AMPL) or any other modeling language. This functionality has been implemented using the “Translator” Module shown in Figure 2. To generate the optimization problem, we use as a training set the available code libraries developed in our previous works [29]. This code library contains python scripts used to solve a variety of optimization problems along with configuration files and network descriptors used to manage our testbed.

The architecture of the transformers for the optimization code generation is shown in Figure 6. For this optimization code, each code block is linked with a specific key and a value. This key acts as a descriptor for the code block which is used by the attention mechanism to identify the subset of code blocks that have the highest correlation with the queries (intents) provided by the user. For the scenario under consideration, the translator has been configured to autogenerate optimization code (in python programming language) for integer linear programming (ILP), mixed ILP (MILP) and non-linear programming formulations (NLP) of the following form:

Objective

$$\min \quad (or \max) \quad [f_1(x), f_2(x), \dots, f_k(x)] \quad (5)$$

Subject to

$$g_i(x) \leq 0, i = 1, 2, \dots, m \quad (6)$$

$$h_j(x) = 0, j = 1, 2, \dots, p \quad (7)$$

where $f_i(x)$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, k$ is the optimization function and $g_i(x)$, $h_j(x)$ is the set of inequality and equality constraints, respectively.

To generate the corresponding optimization code the transformer relies on optimization code templates that are appropriately expanded to meet intent requirements. A typical example illustrating the basic operating principles of this concept is shown in Figure 6. An intent of the form:

Table 1. Samples with keys and values used in the training dataset of a Polatis NxN optical switch configured using SCPI command.

POLATIS® Optical Switch SCPI Protocol User Manual		
	Sample command	Description
	<code>:oxc:swit:conn:add <ing-list>,<egr-list></code>	Reconfigures the OXC to add port-pairs to the existing connection state. <ing-list>,<egr-list>: List of ingress and egress ports
	<code>:oxc:swit:conn:sub <ing-list>,<egr-list></code>	Reconfigures the OXC to remove ports from the existing connection state. This command permits individual connections to be disconnected without disturbing the state of other connections.
	<code>*RST</code>	The switch will perform a reset to default settings
	<code>:oxc:swit:conn:stat?</code>	Returns the existing complete switch state in the form of port pair lists ing-list,egr-list, where ing-list and egr-list are channel lists of ingress and egress ports
	<code>:aps:ffp:add <working ports>,<protecting ports></code>	This command adds protection ports in case failure of the working ports.

Transformer Model Inputs	
Key	Value
Function to add a connection between 2 ports	<code>def quick_connect(self, ingress=0, egress=0): self_switch.write(':oxc:swit:conn:add'+'+ports+');</code>
Polatis switch function to delete connection	<code>def quick_delete(self, ingress=0, egress=0): self_switch.write(':oxc:swit:conn:sub'+'+ports+');</code>
Polatis switch function to reset all connections	<code>def reset(self): sleep(.1) self_switch.write('*RST;')</code>
Polatis switch function to show the status of the optical switch	<code>def stat(self): sleep(.1) self_switch.write(':oxc:swit:conn:stat?')</code>

“Create a Ultra Reliable Low Latency Communications (URLLC) slice minimizing optical network energy”

will be processed by the transformer AI model interrelating this query with the keys in the code library that have the maximum probability to satisfy this intent. For this example, the transformer will select from the set of keys the most relevant objective function (i.e., “WK1: Objective minimizing network energy”) and constraints (“WK4: Function adding latency constraints”). The output of the attention mechanism i.e., attention scores, are applied to the “Values” vector associated with these keys:

```
Wv1: def 5G_network_min_energy(self): m.setObjectiveN(____)
Wv2: def add_latency_constraint(self): m.addConstrs(____)
```

which are appended to the python optimization code template.

At the “Services Layer” of the B5G architecture, the output of the auto-generated optimization problem is used to create the necessary configuration files for the orchestrator managing the 5G platform. This includes the 5G Network Slice Templates (NST), the network service descriptors (NSD) and the Virtual Network Function Descriptors (VNFD) required by OSM [30]. VNFDs define the specifications of the Virtual Machines (VMs) that will host the main entities of the mobile communication platform (i.e. virtualized Core and RAN elements), and the actions that need to be performed to ensure that they function appropriately. The NSD contains the network interfaces for the Virtualized Network Function (VNF). Finally, the NSTs are used for creating the virtual links between the various NSDs chaining and combining multiple VNFs. Once all resources and configuration files are available, the OSM can create a Network Slice Instance (NSI) providing the required service.

At the “Infrastructure Layer”, the translator takes as input the virtual link connectivity requirements and generates the

Figure 7: Physical infrastructure used in the testbed. Example of an auto-generated SCPI command in a Polatis all optical switch redirecting input traffic from port 3 to the output port 11.

appropriate configuration files for the underlying optical transport network. A typical example for the Standard Commands for Programmable Instruments (SCPI) of an all optical NxM Polatis switch as documented in the Polatis Optical Switch User manual [31] is shown in Table 1. These commands can be applied to reconfigure the connectivity diagram of the optical network by adding or subtracting ingress/egress port in a switch, to enquire the status of the network or even add protection ports for increased resilience. The description of these commands can be considered as keys by the transformer architecture which can be used to correlated queries with values (python code) creating the scripts needed to configure / reconfigure the network.

5. Implementation and Numerical Examples

The intent-based management framework described above has been validated in a lab environment for the topology shown in Figure 7 extending the experimental set-up demonstrated in the context of the EU project ECO-eNET [32]. Our implementation included integration of RAN and core domains through an optical transport network that operated in a self-organized manner adopting the IBN concept. For the transport network segment, we

rely on multi-vendor SDN-controlled optical and optoelectronic switches with different capabilities (in terms of number of ports, capacity per port, latency) interconnecting the RAN with the Multi-access Edge Compute (MEC) elements and the central cloud where 5G Core functions were placed. The transport network was organized in a hierarchical manner (Figure 1) offering RAN connectivity, collecting and aggregating transport traffic from various cells to a central location. The access network was equipped with switching nodes having limited number of input ports and relatively small capacity (capacity 1/10GbE per port, with SFP, SFP+ and RJ 45 transceivers). A combination of high-end optoelectronic switches with higher capacity and density (10G/40G/100GbE/ports) and an all-optical (Polatis) switch were used to facilitate aggregation and offer connectivity with the core network segment. For the RAN segment, we relied on the open source OpenAirInterface (OAI) platform to implement the 5G-NR functionalities, while for the core the free5GC has been used. Finally, for the compute domain, we consider edge servers attached to the access switches and central cloud servers connected to the aggregation/core switches.

During the initialization phase, the user expresses an intent in free text to “Set up an Energy Aware URLLC slice”. The transformer AI model “generates” the appropriate optimization code that can be used to identify the corresponding URLLC slice. The generation of the optimization code is performed by comparing the intent with the scripts available in the code library and selecting the one with the highest attention score. Figure 8 (a), (b) illustrates the attention scores for the intents “set-up an energy aware URLLC slice” and “create a URLLC slice that is energy aware”, respectively. These intents result in the generation of a python function “def energy_aware_URLLC()” that identifies the optimal placement of UPF nodes and the transport network capacity that minimizes the energy consumption of the URLLC slice. A similar intent can be produced configuring a transport network switch. A typical example is shown in Figure 8 (c), (d) illustrating the attention scores

Figure 8: IBN Lab implementation: (a)-(b) Attention score of a high level intent is translated into an optimization framework. The transformer “generates (selects from the available code libraries)” the appropriate optimization code to be used by MANO. Similar output is produced with different syntax i.e., “Create URLLC slice energy Aware” (c)-(d): Intent translation into configuration policies for a Polatis all optical switch

Figure 9: (a)-(d): Generation of the corresponding OSM descriptors instantiating the URLLC slice in the testbed

when the intents “connection between ports 11-13” and “function to disconnect all connections” are raised, respectively. These intents are translated into the python functions “def quick_connect” and “def reset(self)” described in Table 1, respectively.

The optimization output is then used by the service layer to autogenerate the relevant configuration files (NSD, VNF, NST) for the UPF nodes, along with the necessary interfaces (Figure 9). An example of the auto generated descriptor for the UPF VNF is shown in Figure 9 (a) whereas in Figure 9(b), the uRLLC slice is instantiated. In Figure 9 (c), the infrastructure layer translator generates the commands and config files to establish transport network connectivity. In the current IBN implementation, the Translator has been trained to create the appropriate input for the SBIs used by the SDN optoelectronic and all optical switches. Specifically:

- For the optoelectronic switches (HP ARUBA, CISCO) the LLM translation is performed using YANG data model templates provided by vendors, available online at [34]. Once generated, these configurations are applied to switches using the (OF-CONFIG) and NETCONF.
- For the all-optical-switch (Polatis OST) the Translator creates the appropriate set of SCPI commands to enable/disable specific input/output ports or map an input to an output port. In the current example, the *Virtual*

Link Descriptor (VLD N3) interconnecting the RAN with the UPF through the all-optical switch is implemented by simply generating a SCPI command interconnecting the appropriate input to the appropriate output port.

Figure 10 shows the time it takes for the OSM to instantiate and configure a 5G VNF (e.g. UPF) based on IBN. This procedure includes three intermediate steps: a) Infrastructure Instantiation, where the VMs hosting VNFs are launched with the appropriate network connections, b) Service Initialization during which the VM is configured to provide the required function c) Service Operations

Figure 10: uRLLC slice instantiation time

during which specific actions are performed dynamically by the operator (monitoring, reconfigurations etc.)

In the following figures we examine the performance of the Transformer AI model in terms of complexity and accuracy under different configuration parameters. The accuracy is measured using the masked cross entropy loss function [33]. The dataset used for training comprises 200 python scripts performing network optimization and system configuration. 85% of this dataset has been used for testing while the remaining for validation.

Figure 11 evaluates the impact of the embedding size of the inputs used in the Translator as a function of the loss function and the training time. We observe that as the embedding size increases, the semantic accuracy of the system increases as inputs can be represented more effectively in a higher dimensional space. However, this comes at the cost of increased training time due to the larger number of parameters that should be trained. In this numerical example, results have been extracted using the following parameters: number of heads in the multi-head attention mechanism equal to 8, 3 encoding and 3 decoding layers ($N_x = 3$) and two-layer feedforward network with 256x512 and 512x256, neurons, dropout=0.1 using the ReLU activation function.

Figure 12-Figure 14 examine the impact of the feedforward network topology (number of nodes, activation function and dropout—probability a nodes in a neural network to be dropped out from the analysis) used in the transformer architecture. In Figure 12 we examine the percentage of the feedforward network nodes that are randomly dropped, known as dropout ratio. We observe that as the dropout ratio increases the loss also increases. This indicates that for the current training dataset, a dense feedforward network architecture provides more accurate interface translations. The impact of the type of activation function in the accuracy of the model is examined in Figure 13 where we observe that the ReLU functions provide slightly higher accuracy compared to Sigmoid and tanh.

The impact of the number of neurons in the two-layer feedforward network on the accuracy and training time is examined in Figure 14. The topologies that have been tested include networks with: a) 128 input/128output nodes and hidden nodes ranging from 256 up to 1024 nodes, b) 256 input/256 output nodes and hidden nodes ranging from 256 up to 512 nodes. We observe that as the size of the feedforward network increases, the loss function also increases. However, this gain comes at the cost of increased computational cost. It should be also noted that above this network size the system didn't converge.

The accuracy of the Transformer AI as a function of the number of training epochs is shown in Figure 15, where we observe that as the number of epochs increases, both the training and validation loss decrease. We observe that after 50 training rounds for the given configuration and relatively limited training dataset the system converges to a minimum point.

Finally, we examine the impact of code library size on complexity and accuracy of the transformer model. Increase of the code library appears when the system should be extended with new optimization functions, configuration file templates and data models in order to support new protocols and devices. For example, adding a new device in the system (i.e., CISCO nx-os switch approximately) requires extension of the code library with approximately 200 data model templates [34]. As shown in Figure 16, the increase of the code library results in an increase of the

Figure 11: Loss function and training time as a function of the embedding size.

Figure 12: Loss as a function of dropout for embedding size 256

Figure 13: Impact of Activation function of accuracy.

Figure 14: Impact feedforward network topology.

training time but the expense of accuracy (training loss) with a marginal increase of the loss function.

Figure 15: Loss function as a number of epochs, number of heads =8, embedding size =256, dropout=0.1

Figure 16: Impact of code library size on accuracy and complexity.

6. Conclusions

IBN is an emerging technology concept aiming at increasing the level of intelligence in communication networks. In contrast to contemporary communication systems that rely on manual processes for their configuration, IBN defines a set of tools that automate time consuming tasks. In this direction, the present study developed interfaces that were used to translate high levels intents to policies ready for implementation by a technology agnostic multi-domain transport network supporting B5G infrastructures. These interfaces relied on GenAI and LLMs to simplify the interaction between different layers and domains automating translation and configuration policies from one domain to another. More specifically, the developed framework has been used to support automated operations of B5G infrastructures at: a) *the orchestration layer* translating high level intents provided by network operators expressed in the form of a natural language into auto-generated optimization code and, b) *the infrastructure layer* creating auto-configuration policies for the optical transport network. The semantic accuracy and complexity of the proposed framework to generate appropriate configuration policies has been

experimentally tested over an optical transport network interconnecting the RAN and core networks.

Acknowledgments. The authors would like to acknowledge financial support by the EU funded project 101139133 ECO-eNET .

References

- <https://www.gartner.com/en/information-technology/glossary/network-intelligence-ni>
- ETSI TS 128 312 V17.0.1 (2022-07), Intent driven management services for mobile networks
- [Online]: Intent Based Networking, <https://www.vmware.com/topics/glossary/content/intent-based-networking.html>
- L. Velasco, S. Barzegar, F. Tabatabaieimehr, and M. Ruiz, "Intent-based networking and its application to optical networks [Invited Tutorial]," J. Opt. Commun. Netw. 14, A11-A22 (2022)
- Paola Iovanna, Marzio Puleri, Giulio Bottari, and Fabio Cavaliere, "Intent-based AI system in packet-optical networks towards 6G [Invited]," J. Opt. Commun. Netw. 16, C31-C42 (2024)
- D. Tuncer, M. Charalambides, G. Tangari and G. Pavlou, "A Northbound Interface for Software-based Networks," 2018 14th International Conference on Network and Service Management (CNSM), Rome, Italy, 2018, pp. 99-107.
- A. Leivadreas and M. Falkner, "A Survey on Intent-Based Networking," IEEE Comm. Surveys & Tut., vol. 25, no. 1, pp. 625-655, 2023.
- M. Pham and D. B. Hoang, "SDN applications - The intent-based Northbound Interface realisation for extended applications," 2016 IEEE NetSoft Conference and Workshops (NetSoft), Seoul, Korea (South), 2016, pp. 372-377,
- L. Pang, C. Yang, D. Chen, Y. Song and M. Guizani, "A Survey on Intent-Driven Networks," in IEEE Access, vol. 8, pp. 22862-22873, 2020,
- C. Cleder Machado, J. Araujo Wickboldt, L. Zambenedetti Granville, A. Schaeffer-Filho, "ARKHAM: An Advanced Refinement toolkit for Handling Service Level Agreements in Software-Defined Networking", J. Netw. Comput. Appl. 2017, 90, 1–16
- A. Tzanakaki, M. Anastasopoulos and V. -M. Alevizaki, "Optical Transport Networks Converging Edge Compute and Central Cloud: An Enabler For 6G Services", (invited) 2024 OFC, San Diego, CA, USA, 2024, pp. 1-3.
- A. Sgambelluri, A. Giorgetti, D. Scano, F. Cugini and F. Paolucci, "OpenConfig and OpenROADM Automation of Operational Modes in Disaggregated Optical Networks," in IEEE Access, vol. 8, pp. 190094-190107, 2020/
- A. Vaswani et al., Attention is all you need. NIPS'17. Curran Associates Inc., Red Hook, NY, USA, 6000–6010 (2017).
- Jacob Devlin, Ming-Wei Chang, Kenton Lee, Kristina Toutanova, BERT: Pre-training of Deep Bidirectional Transformers for Language Understanding, <https://arxiv.org/abs/1810.04805>
- [online] 3GPP WG SA5, Ruiyue Xu, Mark Scott, Stephen Mwanje, Enabling intelligence and automation for 5G Advanced Networks, <https://www.3gpp.org/technologies/intent>
- F. Tonini, C. Natalino, M. Furdek, C. Raffaelli and P. Monti, "Network Slicing Automation: Challenges and Benefits," 2020 International Conference on Optical Network Design and Modeling (ONDM), Spain, 2020, pp. 1-6
- O-RAN.WG1.O-RAN-Architecture-Description.v08.00: O-RAN ALLIANCE Working Group 1, O-RAN Architecture Description, Version 8.0, March 2023, available at <https://www.o-ran.org/specifications>
- Alessio Giorgetti, Andrea Sgambelluri, Ramon Casellas, Roberto Morro, Andrea Campanella, and Piero Castoldi, "Control of open and disaggregated transport networks using the Open Network Operating System (ONOS) [Invited]," J. Opt. Commun. Netw. 12, A171-A181 (2020)
- ETSI GR ZSM 011 V2.1.1, Zero-touch network and Service Management (ZSM); Intent-driven autonomous networks; Generic aspects, Sep. 2024

20. Arthur Selle Jacobs, Ricardo José Pfitscher, Ronaldo Alves Ferreira, and Lisandro Zambenedetti Granville. 2018. Refining Network Intents for Self-Driving Networks. In Proceedings of the Afternoon Workshop on Self-Driving Networks (SelfDN 2018). Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 15–21.
21. Y. Tsuzaki and Y. Okabe, "Reactive configuration updating for Intent-Based Networking," 2017 ICOIN, pp. 97-102
22. M. Riftadi and F. Kuipers, "P4/O: Intent-Based Networking with P4," 2019 (NetSoft), Paris, France, 2019, pp. 438-443
23. <https://www.ietf.org/mailman/listinfo/lbnemo>
24. A. S. Jacobs, "Deploying natural language intents with Lumi," in Proc. SIGCOMM Posters Demos China, 2019, pp. 82-84.
25. Machado, C.C.; Wickboldt, J.A.; Granville, L.Z.; Schaeffer-Filho, A. ARKHAM: An Advanced Refinement toolkit for Handling
26. Rodriguez-Vivas A, Caicedo OM, Ordoñez A, Nobre JC, Granville LZ. NORA: An Approach for Transforming Network Management Policies into Automated Planning Problems. Sensors (Basel). 2021
27. Zied Ben Houidi, Dario Rossi, Neural language models for network configuration: Opportunities and reality check, Computer Communications, Volume 193, 2022, Pages 118-125,
28. Diederik P. Kingma and Jimmy Ba, "Adam: A Method for Stochastic Optimization", 2017, <https://arxiv.org/abs/1412.6980>
29. V. -M. Alevizaki, M. Anastasopoulos, A. -I. Manolopoulos and A. Tzanakaki, "Distributed Service Provisioning for Disaggregated 6G Network Infrastructures," in IEEE Transactions on Network and Service Management, vol. 20, no. 1, pp. 120-137, March 2023
30. [Online]: Open source Management and Orchestration (MANO), <https://osm.etsi.org/>
31. POLATIS® Optical Switch SCPI Protocol User Manual, Ver. 7001-008-02, July 2022
32. ECO-eNET project , <https://www.eco-enet.eu/>
33. Z. Teng et al., Fine-Tuning LLMs for Multi-Turn Dialogues: Optimizing Cross-Entropy Loss with KL Divergence for All Rounds of Responses, in Proc. ICMLC '24: Proceedings of the 2024
34. <https://github.com/YangModels/yang>